

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART III. EFFECT OF
HYDROXYL GROUPS IN THE ALCOHOL ON THE
SYNTHESIS OF ESTERS BY LIPASE

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Synthesis of some aliphatic and aromatic esters has been carried out using acetone-dried lipase in order to study the effect of change of the number of hydroxyl groups in the alcohol on the enzymic synthesis of esters.

The synthesis of the following esters was carried out in order to study the effect of change of the number of hydroxyl groups in the alcohol on the synthesis of esters by lipase: ethyl, glycol and glycerine esters of propionic and butyric acids, phenol, resorcinol and pyrogallol esters of benzoic acid. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE I

Esters.	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
Ethyl propionate	3.0	3.9	9.8	14.9	17.1	18.8
Glycol ..	6.3	9.2	19.1	20.8	23.6	22.8
Glycerine ..	15.9	20.1	23.9	35.8	39.2	38.5
Ethyl butyrate	3.23	4.21	11.60	16.80	16.50	...
Glycol ..	7.50	9.70	18.60	21.70	24.80	23.90
Glycerine ..	15.80	18.50	24.90	38.40	37.90	...
Phenol benzoate	2.3	4.8	5.2	11.6	15.6	14.9
Resorcinol ..	1.8	3.7	7.4	9.2	12.8	18.6
Pyrogallol ..	5.4	8.2	19.5	32.8	31.6	...

From the table it is found that in the aliphatic as well as aromatic series, the percentage synthesis of the ester increases as the number of (OH) group increases in the alcohol. Hence, a clear distinction can be made among mono-, di- and trihydroxy alcohols, since the percentage synthesis of ester increases with the increase in the number of (OH) group in the alcohol.

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